

1 **Studying developmental neurotoxicity in iPS stem cells.**

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We use cell culture systems, primary cells from humans, primates and mice, as well as stem cell culture
8 models to study and answer important biologic questions. Here we used an H9-based neuron-astrocyte
9 iPS co-culture system to describe at the level of the transcriptome events associated with developmental
10 neurotoxicity. Cells exposed to a developmental neurotoxin activated inhibitory synaptic factor family
11 member 2B *INSYN2B*. CNS programming was affected with *SOX21* induction occurring in the context of
12 developmental neurotoxicity. Cells activated *AP3B1* and silenced *GFRA1* in response to methyl mercury-
13 or acrylamide-induced developmental neurotoxicity. The most biologically significant molecular
14 consequence of exposure to a developmental neurotoxin appeared to be silencing of neuritin, encoded by
15 *NRN1*.

16 Citations

17 1. Grandjean, P. and Landrigan, P.J., 2006. Developmental neurotoxicity of industrial chemicals. *The*
18 *Lancet*, 368(9553), pp.2167-2178.

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